

North American Academic
Research | Volume 5 | Issue 4 |
April 2022 | Monthly Journal by
TWASP, USA | Impact Factor:
3.75 (2021)

North American Academic Research

Monthly peer reviewed Journal by **The
World Association of Scientists &
Professionals**
TWASP, United States

High Foreign Debt and the Economic Development of Benin

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Accepted April 30,2022

Published June 12,2022

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Funding: Anhui University of Science and Technology, China.

How to cite this article: Abdel Akbar Ademola O T Sanni, Zhenan Xie, Abdel Wadoud Fadikpe, Jean-Emmanuel Romaric Mahu-Se Sossoukpe, Mahu Wetin Houenali Mathias Toho, Ehouma Jacques Allou (2022). High Foreign Debt and the Economic Development of Benin. *North American Academic Research*, 5(4), 369-376. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6635450>

ABSTRACT

Benin is a country with high foreign debt. Its geographical advantages are not obvious and its own resources are also limited. However, its economy has continued to develop for 26 years and has gained a good reputation internationally. In addition to the unremitting efforts of the Benin government and people; the external debt also plays an important role. Since 1990, the country's external debt has continued to increase, but there has been no debt crisis. In recent years, it has been recognized by more and more countries because of the early repayment of debt, and it has a good national reputation. In 2016, President Talon launched the "Reveal Benin Plan" and continued his re-election in 2021, which shows that the implementation of the plan has achieved certain results. The "Reveal of the Benin Plan" requires a large amount of funds to obtain foreign debt with the country's credibility, obtain the right to issue international bonds with stable economic development and social order, and carry out financing in various ways to bring vitality to the development of Benin. Even with outstanding results, the Benin government is soberly aware that countries with high external debt are prone to debt crises, and debt crises are likely to spread throughout the world. Therefore, after "revealing the Benin plan," some adjustments have been made and new plans are under preparation.

Keywords

Benin country, reveal Benin plan, high foreign debt, debt crisis

Introduction

Benin's foreign debt accounts have a high proportion of the national economy. It can be said that Benin is a country with heavy debts and low exports of manufactured goods and resources. The development is an issue

faced by most African countries and an important challenge declared by the United Nation and external debt is an unavoidable issue. From the point of view of credit, the country becomes the only economic agent for borrowing foreign capital, and the country's ability to use and repay foreign debts not only affects the country's reputation, but also affects the development of the national economy. The foreign debt that Benin needs to repay now is as high as 4 billion US dollars, both domestic debt and foreign debt, because of the repayment of interest, new debts appear, and the debts are difficult to use for national economic development, which brings many problems aspects.

Materials and methods

1. State of Benin

Benin's population is about 12 million and an area of 112,622 square kilometers (43,484 square miles). The political capital is Porto-Novo. The official language of Benin is French, and there are more 50 national languages. Radio and TV stations have Fon, Bariba, Yoruba, Dendi, etc. The main religious beliefs are traditional religion (Voodoo), Christianity, Islam, the life expectancy is 59 years for men and 62 years for women, and the currency is 1 CFA (Communaute Financiere Africaine) franc. The current president is Patrice Talon.

Businessman Patrice Talon (1958-) had a remarkable road to success. In the early days, he was called the "King of Cotton" because of his business success, and he began to get involved in politics in the 21st century. In 2006, he provided financial support for Thomas Boni Yayi, the former president of the West African Development Bank, to run for president, so that he was successfully elected president, and helped him to continue to be re-elected in 2011. Because Talon is a close ally of Yayi, of course, will arouse the dissatisfaction of the reactionaries, so after the attempted poisoning of President Yayi in October 2012, Talon was accused of participating in the murder, forcing him to flee to France. The accusation should be false, Talon himself denied it, and the investigation results have nothing to do with him, so he was granted a presidential pardon in May 2014 and returned to Benin in October 2015. The incident brought Talon to fame and thus to his candidacy for the presidency. In March 2016, after two rounds of voting, Talon successfully defeated the ruling party candidate Lionel Zinsou and was elected as the eighth president of the Republic of Benin. 86 % of the votes and was re-elected for a five-year term.

Talon, a businessman, has neither public management experience nor political experience, but his successful business experience has laid the foundation for his governance. Since taking office in 2016, with the main purpose of new thinking and new ideas, the "2016-2021 Government Action Plan" (hereinafter referred to as "Reveal Benin Plan") has been formulated, and comprehensive reforms have been implemented, trying to make Benin embark on a "new journey". According to the "Reveal Benin Plan", agriculture, tourism and services are the priority areas for development. Agriculture mainly focuses on cotton production, and

develops foreign exchange-earning agricultural products, such as cashew nuts and oil palms; tourism gives full play to the functions of original scenic spots, develops new scenic spots with historical and cultural characteristics, and improves tourism facilities, making them gradually become the main economic pillars of the country. The service industry focuses on infrastructure construction and improvement of service quality, attracts by improving the investment environment, and achieves the purpose of attracting foreign investment to develop the economy. In general, "energy for all" is required, so new technology industries are developed, the digital economy is vigorously developed, and the privatization process is accelerated. The reform can be said to be effective, and its economy is generally stable, but there are also some problems, such as the resistance to the free market reform plan, a series of public sector strikes, especially the foreign debt accumulated over the years, which are all problems that need to be solved urgently.

2. Reasons of Benin's External Debt

After the 1970s, characterized by prudent and rigorous economic management, the 1980s began with major shocks (low growth rate, huge arrears accumulation, unsustainable budget deficits), which plunged the economic development path of developing countries into a serious crisis. In the mid-1980s, in the face of growing financing needs, cash flow difficulties forced countries to turn heavily to external sources of financing. Although the external debt burden has been reduced in various ways, it has become an obstacle to the development of third world countries under the coexistence of multiple determinants such as low savings level, severe balance of payments situation, and low interest rates, recorded economic growth. The emergence of these countries caused serious external debt service problems in the 1980s and highlighted the potentially catastrophic consequences of excessive borrowing for these less developed countries. As a result, the inability to implement solvency-appropriate debt policies disrupts capital flows, which can undermine economic growth and stability, especially if the share of private capital increases substantially. In Benin, the economic downturn in the early 1980s, as a result of a worsening balance of payments deficit and accelerating debt growth, put Benin's real capacity level at a critical juncture. The economy to cope with the need for external financing and the level of debt sustainability. Gross debt outstanding as a share of GDP from 79.15% in 1990 to 82.64% in 1994, before falling back to 19.2% in 2007. It is worth noting that in initiatives supporting Heavily Indebted Poor Countries (HIPC), this ratio has been below 50% since 2002. As for export-related debt service, the change was about the same as the outstanding amount, showing from 31.19% in 1990 to 22.55% in 1994, and then 4.5% in 2007. These data suggest that the country's investment capacity has declined, which has increased its reliance on external financing.

3. Benin External Debt Structure

Benin's national external debt consists of multilateral debt and bilateral debt. From the perspective of the development of external debt from 1990 to 2017, the proportion of outstanding external debt continued to grow, while the proportion of repaid external debt was relatively stable, showing a continuous decline in repayment capacity (see Table 1).

Figure 1 Outstanding External Debt and External Debt/GDP Change (%) from 1990 to 2017

As at 31 December 2017, the total debt borne by creditors of Benin's national multilateral institutions was US\$ 2467846859.21, Its main lenders are the International Development Association (IDA) and the West African Development Bank (BOAD). Other borrowers are European Investment Bank (EIB), International Fund for African Development (BADEA), Islamic Development Bank (IDB), Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC), International Monetary Fund (IMF), African Development Bank Group (AFDB) ... Even so, the allocation of funds and replenishment of resources cannot be guaranteed, because these resources have not been mainly used for production activities. It should also be noted that, even for income-generating projects, management issues often prevent the replenishment of resources needed, resulting in the failure to provide regular debt repayments, so the provision of debt financing to public enterprises is significant.

Aside from the issue of cross-agency allocation of credit, efficiency is not always an important factor in funding programs. Because the return on investment is not as good as expected, foreign debt directly affects the development of the national economy. On the one hand, it exacerbates the deterioration of the terms of trade and on the other hand, there are borrowing risks in allocation and management, which in turn makes financing more difficult and restricts economic development.

¹ World Bank Data.

Debt repayment is not just a matter of measuring the amount of debt, but has become an important issue in the management of resources both inside and outside a country. In general, the financial resource pressure of debtor countries depends on the level of loans and their interest rates. Benin is a multilaterally indebted country, and borrowers offer credit terms that highlight interest rates, repayment and currency terms, as well as layoffs. (For loan interest rate and term, see Table 1)

Table 1 Conditions under which multilateral creditors grant credit

creditor	loan currency	Refund currency	average interest rate	year due	Deferred years
AID	\$UB -DTS	\$UB-Euro	0.75%	40	10
BADEA	\$UB	\$UB	2%	13-16	5-6
BEI	Euro	Euro	1%	5-40	4
BID	DI	DI-\$UB	2.5%	15-25	3-7
BOAD	FCFA	FCFA	3.025%	18	5-7
FIDA	DTS	Euro	0.75%	30	10
Fonds CEDEAO	UCAO	Euro	4%	14	4
Fonds OPEP	\$UB	\$UB	1%	12-20	5
FAD	UC	\$UB	0.75%	50	6-7
FSN	UC	\$UB	2%	24	4
FMI	DTS	Euro	0.5%	15	5

Data source: CAA. December 31, 1986 was the first year of statistics, and before the adjustment program, AID had provided Benin with 26 loans to undertake loan commitments of 79 billion CFA francs. During this period, CFA 57 billion has been paid and AID deducted FCFA 55.4 billion in Benin. From 1989, after Benin received international financing (after the signing of the first PAS), multilateral debt exploded.

In addition to multilateral debts, the Benin State has many bilateral debts, that is, credit loans formed by the government or specialized agencies of the government, or by private or public banks in another country.

This type of debt comes in many forms, such as: direct debt of the state; state-sanctioned debt where the state intervenes only in the default events; unpaid debts paid by the beneficiary but not guaranteed by the state.

Table 2 Conditions under which bilateral donors grant credit

Holder	Loan Currency	Refund Currency	Average interest rate	Loan Duration	Deferred years
Kuwait	DK	DK	5%	17	6
China	YUAN RMB	Nature or devise	1%	10–25	10
Japan	Yen	Yen	0% to 1%	30	10
France	Euro	Euro	2.25%	10–30	3–10
USA	USA\$	USA\$	2.25%	25	9
Belgium	Euro	Euro	0%	12–25	3–10
Russia	RBL	USA\$	2.25%	18	10

Data source: CAA. Benin's bilateral debt portfolio is very diverse in terms of active diplomacy implemented in cooperation with the rest of the world. As with multilateral debt, the Benin State's contribution to development finance can often be seen by understanding credit and the conditions attached to it in the external debt process. France remains the main partner in the financing of Benin's economy, intervening through advances from the Ministry of Finance or through loans. With the advancement of China's "One Belt, One Road" initiative, Benin has brought new development opportunities, such as preferential loans and assistance for the construction of Benin's national broadband network.

Since 1989, the outstanding external debt of the country of Benin has risen more or less steadily before and after the devaluation of the franc. From 1990 to 1993, the outstanding multilateral debts were 56.3%, 60.9%, 61.4% and 63.6%, and the bilateral debts were 43.7%, 39.1%, 38.6% and 36.4% respectively. The ratio of outstanding debt to GDP in debt is also unstable, but the external debt service ratio (Debt Service Ratio) is not proportional to export earnings. According to the formula for calculating the foreign debt repayment ratio, the amount of debt repayment in the current year/the amount of foreign exchange receipts from the export of goods and services in the current year $\times 100\%$. In Benin, the rates were 62.62%, 45.88%, 93.73%, 48.47%, 26.38% in 1994, and 30.52% in 1995. This ratio is contained within the acceptable threshold of 25% of the balance of export earnings using capital goods import transactions, and has remained around

3% from 1996 to 20082. According to international general rules, the foreign debt repayment rate of 20% is a safety index. Benin has always been within the safety index, so there has not been a major crisis in borrowing.

The ratio of insurance debt service to government revenue, showing the proportion of total revenue used to service the country's external debt. This ratio is not high in the State of Benin because the budget is basically fiscal, so that most of the resources are devoted to the import of capital goods, project financing and the payment of salaries of civil servants. According to Benin's national budget for 2022, the growth rate will reach 7%, and the budget deficit will account for 4.5% of GDP, indicating that the ratio of dependence on external debt has declined, and the financing capacity has been strengthened.

4. National economy dependent on foreign debt

The Heavily Indebted Poor Countries Initiative (HIPC), launched by the International Monetary Fund and the World Bank in 1996, has revived the debate on the relationship between external debt and economic growth, but it cannot be denied that the heavy debt burden has constrained Africa Economic development, the implementation of HIPC will be beneficial to the sustainable economic development of Africa, but it will inevitably bring about political and cultural conflicts, which will affect the development of African society.

The implementation of the HIPC program over the past 30 years has enabled developing countries to benefit from a large number of loans and achieve rapid economic take-off. It is worth noting that some developing countries have peaked their debt ratios and have to face repayment problems. For these developing countries, the repayment of these debts is not only a constraint on economic development, but also becomes an impossible task, which leads to a debt crisis. The crisis, which began in the 1980s, invalidated FAO and the International Fund for Agricultural Development (FIDA) and required the active participation of multilateral institutions, including the International Monetary Fund and the World Bank.

In the 1970s, some developing countries fell into debt crises, but the large surpluses of oil exporters allowed high debt growth rates while reducing the excess international liquidity accumulated by banks. Short-term interest rates have risen sharply as US Federal Reserve President Paul Volcker pursued a tightening of monetary policy against inflation, unavoidably placing many unexpected burdens on borrowing countries. The strong appreciation of the U.S. dollar against the foreign exchange market not only increases the debt burden denominated in U.S. dollars, but changes in exchange rates directly affect the economic development of various countries, leading to inflation in some developing countries, collapse of commodity prices, and paralysis of the terms of trade. The foreign debt is repaid, the debt crisis is plunged into a spiral of hell, and African countries bear the brunt.

² World Bank Data.

In fact, the impoverishment of Africa is directly related to its debt. The spiral of debt in hell has made the debt burden so high that some countries have had to devote considerable budgets to repaying the debt, which is still difficult to repay, and can only borrow new debts, making the debt tirelessly inflated. Africa's external debt rose from \$6 billion in 1980 to \$231 billion in 1999. Rapidly growing debt will of course lead to higher repayments. Sub-Saharan Africa's debt repayment rate is four times the combined health and education budget, which not only directly affects economic development, but also exacerbates social unrest and affects the international community, stability of order. Faced with this situation, the International Monetary Fund and the World Bank launched the Heavy Poor Countries Initiative (HIPC), which aims to create conditions for countries to continue to receive funding. The implementation of the HIPC plan is conducive to the deployment of public expenditures in the social sector of heavily indebted poor countries, making their debts sustainable, creating conditions for their economic growth, and focusing on enhancing the country's productive capacity, thereby alleviating the debt crisis.

The implementation of the HIPC plan has brought opportunities to Benin's economic development. The annual economic growth rate target of 7% can lift most of the population out of poverty, which is also the minimum level required to reduce poverty. The current President Talon formulated the "Reveal Benin Plan" at the beginning of his administration, hoping that the country can develop sustainably and achieve considerable achievements, but some problems inevitably arise, such as low productivity and a lack of credibility in the legal system, weak resources allocated to the national economy, inadequate infrastructure, etc. To make up for the shortfall in resources, turning to external debt without thinking that the HIPC program is not beneficial to the Benin country.

The HIPC program sets thresholds for debt ratios designed to determine the sustainability of poor countries' debt. Following an initial assessment, in July 1997 the agencies declared Benin's national debt sustainable, thereby preventing it from benefiting from the HIPC scheme. In fact, the debt relief that Benin received in the debt restructuring program, combined with the improving economic situation, has led to a reduction in debt, making it possible to achieve debt sustainability within specified limits. It was pointed out that the calculations made were not without problems, as Benin was a transit country to neighboring countries, especially Nigeria. The balance-of-payments statistics method recommended by the International Monetary Fund is based on the principle of change of ownership. Since direct transit does not imply a change of ownership, this amount was deducted from the export amount, which resulted in an increase in Benin's national net present value (NPV) and the external debt ratio of exports from 158% to 222% between 1996 and 1998, so in 1998 Benin's national foreign debt was declared unsustainable.

Debt sustainability analysis is limited to calculating debt ratios over two or three years and making short- and medium-term forecasts based on scenarios as the economic situation evolves to determine whether debt is sustainable. Benin has benefited from the HIPC program and multilateral debt reduction since 2003, thanks

to sound macroeconomic policies and major structural reforms. At the critical decision point, when the country officially enters the HIPC program, the amount of relief it should receive is calculated. Most of these reductions will take effect when the country completes the process, i.e. when the completion point is reached, with only a small amount of relief available in the interim phase. The general measures required to achieve the completion point are: satisfactory implementation of the full poverty reduction strategy for at least one year; use of debt service savings in accordance with the terms agreed at the decision point; in accordance with the terms of the IMF Poverty Enhancement Program and macroeconomic performance good. The country of Benin has generally achieved the completion point, and thus obtained a good reputation, which has also laid the foundation for the use of foreign debt to vigorously develop its own economy.

5. Coping strategies under heavy debt

Even if Benin's foreign debt is declared unsustainable, in 2016, President Talon formulated the "Reveal Benin Plan" at the beginning of his administration. It can be seen that the Benin government is full of confidence in the future, and it is also in line with national conditions to identify agriculture, tourism and service industries as priority areas for development.

President Talon said in his inauguration speech: "We urgently need political reforms, reorganization of the national economy, by improving the social structure, to enhance the new confidence of citizens, and to develop the economy to restore the credibility of our country." The "Reveal Benin Plan" clearly states that its goal during the presidency is to make the country's fundamental reforms full of dynamism.

The Revealing Benin Plan has three pillars, seven key priorities, 45 flagship projects, 95 sector-specific projects, and 19 institutional reform projects. The so-called three pillars: strengthening the construction of democracy, consolidating the status of the country under the rule of law, and improving the governance capacity of the government; promoting the structural transformation and improvement of the economy; and improving the living conditions of the people. Seven key priorities: strengthening the foundation of democracy and the rule of law; improving governance; reforming the macroeconomic framework to maintain stable economic growth; strengthening infrastructure; improving education and research; strengthening social basic services and social protection; regional balance and sustainable development. The 45 flagship projects are under the direct responsibility of the Office of the President, with funding and oversight from public-private partners. 95 industry-specific projects are under the responsibility of relevant departments, and priority industries will receive funding and preferential support. The 19 institutional reforms aim to create a more democratic framework to enhance the effectiveness of governance.

The "Reveal Benin Plan" emphasizes that the Benin State is a model of democracy and stability, and its inclusiveness can bring vitality to the sustainable development of the economy, contribute to social progress, and also have the potential for future development. Benin's strategic location in West Africa, as well as its

human capital, political stability and cultural heritage, and social development potential, have indisputable advantages. Under this circumstance, the purpose of implementing the "Reveal Benin Plan" is to create an environment for talent development, so that the people of Benin can be full of vitality, so as to complete the country's long-term plan and achieve rejuvenation. The "Revealing Benin Plan" is a major project involving political system, economic development and social stability, which is an important pillar of national development. 45 flagship projects, 95 industry-specific projects, and 19 institutional reforms will be supported by the state to realize the cooperation between the state and private enterprises. It will be an unprecedented scale of investment, which will help promote employment, improve social welfare, and create social wealth. . This "new impetus" of development will facilitate the formation of partnerships between our economic sector and other countries and private enterprises, and will also help to enhance the international image of Benin as a country, and more importantly, it will enable every Benin citizen can use their talents and vitality³.The implementation effect of the "Reveal Benin Plan" is obvious. In recent years, the economy has continued to grow and people's lives have been improved. In July 2020, the country of Benin was placed in the lower-middle-income economy category by the World Bank, which speaks volumes.

The "Reveal Benin Plan" is entirely a government-guided action, and the implementation of various projects also relies on the national budget, which requires a lot of funds. Benin's national economic source is mainly agriculture and storehouse trade, and its industrial base is weak. Resources are also relatively poor, tourism resources are not fully utilized, and the state can obtain limited financial resources. In 2020 statistics, the GDP is \$14.4 billion, the GDP growth rate is -3%, and the inflation rate is 1.3%⁴. The investment in the "Reveal Benin Plan" has exceeded the gross national product, so the degree of dependence on external debt is very high.

Benin has a stable society, its economy has been developing continuously for 26 years, and it has a good reputation internationally, so it is relatively easy to obtain foreign aid. In addition to receiving long-term assistance from France for historical reasons, countries and international institutions such as Denmark, Germany, China, the United States, Japan, the Netherlands, the World Bank, the European Union, the African Development Fund, the West African Development Bank and the International Monetary Fund have also Actively participating, the average annual assistance is about 580 million US dollars, mainly for health, education and training, agricultural development, export promotion, etc., to ensure the orderly implementation of the "Reveal Benin Plan". Because of the increasing national credibility, in May 2020, the country of Benin successfully issued government bonds in the West African Economic and Monetary Union (UEMOA) regional market, raising more than 50 billion CFA francs. In January 2021, Benin became the first country in Africa to

³ GOVERNMENT ACTION PROGRAMME 2016-2021 SUMMARY.

⁴ London Quarterly Economic Survey July - September 2021.

issue international bonds, with a total issuance of 1 billion euros, or about 656 billion West African francs. The injection of these funds will promote the development of the national economy of Benin.

It is worth noting that highly indebted countries are prone to debt crises. The large amount of financial resources that Benin's country has received in a short period of time, while benefiting its economic development, has also exposed it to a debt crisis. According to the internationally recognized ratio of the principal and interest of the current year to export earnings is 20%, which is a warning line, the Benin is currently receiving a large amount of new foreign debt, even if it exceeds the warning line. However, with the passage of time, the repayment of the principal and interest of the debt will be more and more, relying on debt repayment will become a problem, and even lead to the country's dishonesty, it is difficult to obtain aid and foreign investment, it will easily lead to a national economic collapse. There are three important factors in overcoming the external debt crisis. First, a favorable international economic environment will enable debtor countries to reduce their actual financing costs. Second, the ability of debtor countries to adjust themselves to stabilize the macroeconomic and rational economic structure to improve the efficiency of the use of foreign debt; Third, control the flow of funds from debtor countries to creditor countries, encourage direct investment and adopt securities investment. The Government of Benin seems to have a relatively clear understanding of the debt crisis and to have grasped these three important factors, making full use of the country's credibility to raise capital; Obtaining the right to issue international bonds is also conducive to financing in many aspects; There will also be macroeconomic and structural adjustments, such as September 18, 2021, just 100 days into President Talon's second term, The construction of the Glo-Djigbé international airport, one of the flagship projects of Project Reveal Benin, was delayed, in order, according to the Government spokesman, to allow for better investment in other areas, apparently adjustments.

Conclusion

Benin is an indebted country. Although after 26 years of stable economic development, the society is relatively stable and people's living standards have generally improved, it has not been able to completely change the situation of high debt and there is a potential debt crisis. It is important to know that a country's debt crisis may lead to a global debt crisis, especially for countries with high debts that involve a wide range of debts, which is more likely to trigger a global crisis. If it happens, it will be a tragedy for mankind. Benin can realize this and make continuous efforts to ensure the orderly development of its own economy under the premise of development, which is also a contribution to the world. Looking forward to the end of the "Reveal Benin Plan", there will be an updated plan.

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